

A Study on Training and Development in Private Sector Banks in Thiruvarur Town

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Abstract

The banking sector of India becoming more competitive. Now-a- days the public and private sector banks perform well and competing with each other. The continuous changes in business environment, the banking sector also continuously enhance and improve knowledge and skill sets across the organization. Training to adopt to the changing banking present context which we find as today. Training and Development programme is the framework for helping bank employees. To develop their personal and organisation skills, knowledge, ability through employee training and development. Employee will always want to develop career enhancing skills which will always head to employee motivation and retention. Since globalization enormous amount of changes have taken place in banking industry in terms of its products and services. More innovative activity has gone in to the process of Human Resources Development. The well trained employees are the valuable assets of the bank. But even employers still facing a shortage of candidates with the right skill and experience to fill critical job. This paper reviews the Impact of training and development on the employees of banking sector.

Keywords: Training and development, Banking sector

Introduction

In banking sector Training and Development programme must adopt inputs which enables the participants to gain skills learn theoretical concepts and help acquire vision to look into the distant future. Nowadays banks have realized the importance of training and re-training their staff to develop a competitive edge over the competitors delivering high quality services.

In banking sector Training and Development refer imparting of specific skills, abilities and knowledge to an employee. To establish match between employee and his job. Training and Development of the staff is a continuous process in banking sector in the area of customer care service on operational aspects and behavioural aspects of the business. To prepare an employee for future assignment. To people within many profession and occupation especially in banking sector may refer to this sort of Training and Development as a

professional development. This training program increase the performance level of employees and reduce the wastage, accidents and meeting future employee's needs.

According to (Stephen Stumpf May to June 2010) company functioning in India training on products and operations is imparted through internet based training modules.

The bank has built competency across various sector. Training thus provide certain advantages which are not available by training through experience. Special programmes on functional training and leadership development conducted to build knowledge as well as management ability at a dedicated training facility.

Review of Literture

This chapter is one such an attempt on review the earlier studies related to the present are of the study.

Megharaja.B (2014): The author mentioned that training methodologies to employees has to planned and organized activity to impart skills and techniques. Training program will improve the productivity of an employee in effective and efficient manner. It is important in Human Development process in organization but also both private and public bank are competing each other to perform well. Changes in globalization amount of changes in banking industry in terms products and services. So that author conclude that need for employee training to adapt to the changing in bank

Jyoti (2017): The author mentioned that there is rapidly changing in business environment in banking sector to improve their knowledge and skills. Banks are facing several critical problem. The author conclude the impact of training and development on the employees in bank effectively

Mohanraj.P (2014): The author said that training and development is the framework for bank employee to develop their personal skill, knowledge and abilities. Employees want to develop career-enhancing skills for their retention and employee motivation. The author conclude to develop and trained staff are valuable assets for bank which increasing the chances of his efficiency of her duties.

Kavita Rani, Diksha Gara (2014): The author mentioned that the training has attached effectively in development of baking sector. Indian banking industry continuously going through a process of transformation since nineties, due to the introduction of Liberalization, privatization and Globalization (LPG), information and communication (ICT) to extent the training and development program to bank for their employees and shows the effectiveness of program to bank employees. The author conclude giving suggestions to enhance training and development strategies due to competition so that employees have many challenges so effectiveness in training and development.

Nagar (2009): The author mentioned that in commercial banks in public as well as in private bank there should have effectiveness training programmes has to be conduct. The author concluded that the study focus is mainly the opinions of the trainees shows various aspects of training like course duration, library Facilities, trainer, teaching and computer aided programmes and other infrastructural facilities.

Mohanty (2011): The author explained that Liberalization, privatization and Globalization (LPG) have changed in worldwide and facing many challenges. In training we needed to provide new skills and abilities to bank employees facing many challenges. Training is important in motivated human resources to improve overall performance in an organization. The author concluded that training making employees more effective and productive.

Objectives

- To analyse the impact of Training and Development for employees serving in bank
- To examine the effectiveness of training towards job and personal growth.

Research Methodology

This research depends on the systematic collecting the data and analysing in sequential order. The study based on primary and secondary data. Primary data collected through questionnaires. The secondary data includes reference books, journal, research papers and internet. First-hand information was collected from 50 respondents of banking sector in thiruvavarur district. Stratify random sampling method was employed for selecting in the respondent from the selected district. The study is carried out in private banks like Axis Bank, City Union Bank, Karur Vyshya Bank in Thiruvavarur.

Analysis and Interpretation

The data analysis to determine effectiveness of training and development.

Table 1
Employees Acquired Technical Knowledge and Skill through Training

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Respondent
Strongly Agree	24	48
Agree	20	40
Neutral	-	-
Disagree	5	10
Strongly Disagree	1	2
Total	50	100

Interpretation

From the Table above we can understand that, majority of 48% of the employees strongly agree that employees acquired technical knowledge and skill through training, 40% of the employees agree, 10% of the employees disagree, 2% of the employees strongly disagree.

Table 2
Training Increases the Skill of Employees

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Respondent
Strongly Agree	25	50
Agree	22	44
Neutral	-	-
Disagree	3	6
Strongly Disagree	-	-
Total	50	100

Interpretation

From the Table above we can understand that, majority of 50% of the employees strongly agree that training increases the skill of employees, 44% of the employees agree, 6% of the employees disagree.

Table 3
The Training Program Helpful in Personal Growth

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Respondent
Strongly Agree	18	36
Agree	12	24
Neutral	1	2
Disagree	9	18
Strongly Disagree	10	20
Total	50	100

Interpretation

From the Table above we can understand that, majority of 36% of the employees strongly agree that training program helpful in personal growth, 24% of the employees agree, 2% of the employees neutral, 18% of the employees disagree, 20% of the employees strongly disagree.

Table 4
Training Program Helped to Reduce the Difficulties in Job

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Respondent
Strongly Agree	17	34
Agree	13	26
Neutral	2	4
Disagree	9	18
Strongly Disagree	9	18
Total	50	100

Interpretation

From the Table above we can understand that, majority of 36% of the employees strongly agree that training program helpful to reduce the difficulties in job, 26% of the employees agree, 4% of the employees neutral, 18% of the employees disagree, 18% of the employees strongly disagree.

Table 5
Training and Development Reduce the Stress Level of Employees

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Respondent
Strongly Agree	22	44
Agree	8	16
Neutral	5	10
Disagree	11	22
Strongly Disagree	4	8
Total	50	100

Interpretation

From the Table above we can understand that, majority of 44% of the employees strongly agree that training and development reduce the stress level of employees, 16% of the employees agree, 10% of the employees neutral, 22% of the employees disagree, 8% of the employees strongly disagree.

Conclusion

Based on the research study the Training and Development should offer graduate programme to employees. This will create work enjoyment and job challenging. To provide training and development programme effectively, employee enhance their knowledge and skills to satisfy the customers. The training and development programmes reduce the wastage, spoiling of working time and also help in personal growth of employees. Employees stress reduced by the way of work enjoyment. Training and development important because of the ever changing environment and technology especially in banking sector. The training make employee more effective and productive.

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